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Mega-constellation satellites: Assessing their interference on ground-based astronomy

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Abstract

With the projected significant growth of mega-constellations in the near-future, the existence of these large Earth-orbiting satellite networks presents an increasing threat to astronomical research. Focusing on the SpaceX Starlink network as a representative case, this work utilises observations from the MASCARA wide-field imaging array to assess the present and future impact of mega-constellations on ground-based optical astronomy.

1605 observations of Starlink satellite trails were collected over a single observing night in October 2022. Visual brightness magnitudes were computed for each observation using routines to detect and extract trails from the data, finding an average magnitude of 5.8 ± 0.10 with a standard deviation of 0.95. The design modifications developed by SpaceX to mitigate the brightness were investigated, finding an average magnitude of 5.9 ± 0.09 for its v1.5 design (the latest version deployed at the time of this study). Although this was found to be an improvement to its previous VisorSat design, further considerations are required to minimize the impact on observations.

Images captured in the first and last hour were found to be most affected, with approximately 39% containing at least one trail. As these observations fall inside peak observing times, the presence of these trails have the potential to hinder science objectives. The level of interference was examined by determining the percentage of the MASCARA FoV obscured. While the highest value only reached 0.18%, this became more significant when extrapolated to future population sizes. For the expected Starlink population (40 000), a maximum of 5.2% was found, whereas a maximum exceeding 65% was determined for the expected population of all mega-constellations (500 000). This means that hundreds of satellites could be visible in MASCARA observations at peak observing times.

The results presented in this work provide valuable insight into the scale of interference caused by mega-constellations on ground-based astronomy. It is evident that these satellites have the ability to frequently contaminate observations and potentially impact science operations. These effects should be considered by ground-based surveys and mitigation strategies should be developed to preserve uninterrupted astronomical research.

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Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Research Objectives	2
2	Background and Theory	3
2.1	Mega-constellations	3
2.1.1	Starlink	4
2.2	Orbital elements	6
2.3	MASCARA	7
2.3.1	Science case	8
2.3.2	Data handling	9
3	Methodology	12
3.1	Satellite visibility	12
3.2	Recognising satellite trails	15
3.3	Extracting satellite trails	16
3.3.1	Suppressing noise	17
3.3.2	Line detection	19
3.4	Brightness magnitudes	22
3.5	Error propagation	25
4	Results	28
4.1	Photometric study	29
4.2	Geometric study	32
4.3	Science interference	34
5	Discussion	38
5.1	Sources of uncertainty	38
5.2	Future work	39
5.2.1	Improvements and additional considerations	39
5.2.2	Beyond MASCARA	41
5.2.3	Additional data	41

6	Conclusions	43
	Appendices	49
A	Tabulated Starlink properties	49
B	Bright outliers	50

Acronyms

ASCC All-Sky Compiled Catalogue

CCD Charge Coupled Device

FOTOS Feasibility study for Optical Tracking of Orbital Satellites

FoV Field-of-View

GEO Geostationary Orbit

HT Hough Transform

LEO Low Earth Orbit

MASCARA Multi-site All-Sky CAmeRA

MEO Medium Earth Orbit

NORAD North American Aerospace Defense Command

RANSAC Random Sample Consensus

RMS Root Mean Square

SGP Simplified General Perturbations

TLE Three-Line Element set

1 Introduction

In recent years, the development of large satellite networks has become increasingly prominent in the field of space technology. These so-called mega-constellations can consist of several hundred or even thousands of individual artificial satellites, creating a celestial-like arrangement with a resemblance to stellar constellations in the night sky (Witze, 2022). The primary objective of these vast satellite arrays is to provide extensive data coverage, with the largest companies involved attempting to achieve internet connectivity on a global scale. While the services provided by mega-constellations hold the potential to revolutionize various industries, their presence sparks a number of concerns within the scientific community and, in particular, among astronomers.

Through the ages, astronomers have relied on dark, unpolluted skies to observe and resolve celestial objects in our Universe. While space-based observatories have the advantage of making observations unobstructed by the Earth's atmosphere, these are very costly endeavours that require significant development and deployment times. Ground-based observatories, on the other hand, are much more accessible and easier to maintain, which is why they are more numerous and widely used within the field (Currie et al., 2018). This accessibility enables ground-based facilities to perform extensive surveys and long-term monitoring of celestial objects, contributing to comprehensive studies of phenomena like exoplanets, galaxies, and transient events to name but a few.

However, as mega-constellations grow in size, so does the threat of interference on ground-based observations (Venkatesan et al., 2020). As these satellites orbit the Earth, they can reflect light from the Sun towards the ground, increasing their visibility and often making them bright enough to be detected in images captured by ground-based telescopes. This contamination can become increasingly worse for observations taken over long exposure times, which are often adopted for ground-based surveys of the night sky. As a satellite moves over the exposure time, it can leave a characteristic streak or trail across the image, with a greater possibility of leaving longer trails over longer exposure times. These trails may obscure regions of the sky that are of potential interest and, hence, interfere with the science objectives of the observation.

While the presence of satellite trails may affect telescopes operating at different wavelength ranges, the scale of this interference varies depending on the type of telescope in

question (Long, 2021). Studies have shown that observations in near-infrared and sub-mm wavelengths can be impacted by satellite trails (Walker et al., 2020), while more recent evidence has confirmed that radio observations are being increasingly affected by radiation emitted by mega-constellations (Di Vruno et al., 2023). However, these satellites do not emit a significant amount of radiation when compared to the sunlight that is reflected off them. The large majority of ground-based observatories consist of optical telescopes that capture visible light. With an abundance of these light sources extending throughout space, the visible portion of the electromagnetic spectrum offers a rich source of information for studying the universe. As optical instruments are most affected by visible light reflections, it is these telescopes that are typically the most susceptible to contamination by trails (Hainaut & Williams, 2020).

1.1 Research Objectives

As of July 2023, 18 mega-constellations with a combined total of 543 811 satellites have been planned for launch in the near-future¹. With interference to astronomy already a present issue (Lalbakhsh et al., 2022), one can only expect the scale of this problem to grow as more and more of the night sky is populated over time. As we are not long after the advent of mega-constellation deployments, a qualitative assessment of their interference on ground-based astronomy could provide key insights into the magnitude of their affect. Investigating the level at which current populations impact observations may yield results that could inspire future satellite design and deployment strategies with increased consideration for the astronomical community. Motivated by these implications, this thesis project set out to do the following:

1. Further develop and extend automated routines for detecting satellite trails in ground-based observational data.
2. Examine the variation in satellite illumination to evaluate the conditions for which these satellites are most visible to the ground.
3. Assess the impact of satellite trails in observational images by investigating properties like their design, frequency of occurrence, and brightness magnitude.
4. Explore relationships that may exist between different orbital parameters to characterize the conditions that most affect the brightness of a satellite.
5. Quantify the current and estimated future extent of interference caused by these satellites on ground-based optical astronomy.

By carrying out these objectives, this thesis seeks to address the growing concern posed by mega-constellations towards astronomical observations.

¹ See <https://planet4589.org/space/con/conlist.html> for updated statistics (McDowell, 2023).

2 Background and Theory

2.1 Mega-constellations

The majority of Earth-orbiting satellites fall into three classifications based on their altitude ([Montenbruck & Gill, 2000](#)). Satellites in Geostationary Orbit (GEO) are located highest, with altitudes around 35000 km above the equator. These orbit with the same rotational velocity as Earth, allowing them to remain fixed relative to a given position on the ground. With the ability to provide continuous coverage to a specific region, these satellites are typically used for telecommunications and large scale weather monitoring. Below this, satellites in a Medium Earth Orbit (MEO) are generally positioned between 2000 and 35000 km above the equator. These satellites maintain a wide coverage while benefiting from a lower latency compared to satellites at a greater distance in GEO, and so are typically used for GPS services. Finally, satellites in a Low Earth Orbit (LEO) have orbital altitudes below 2000 km. These have a multitude of uses including weather monitoring, communication services, and high resolution Earth observation.

As a result of their smaller orbital distances, the low latency achieved by LEO satellites make them ideal for providing high-speed internet services. However, the curvature of the Earth restricts a satellite’s line of sight at low altitudes, limiting its coverage. Therefore, large satellite networks known as mega-constellations are required to achieve internet connectivity on a global scale ([Zhang et al., 2022](#)). Due to technical advancements in recent years, the ability to build cheaper and smaller spacecraft has driven the development of mega-constellations by large commercial businesses like Amazon, Airbus, Boeing, and SpaceX ([Byers & Boley, 2023](#)).

With the populations of mega-constellations steadily increasing and future plans to have several hundreds of thousands of satellites in LEO, scientists are becoming increasingly worried about the potential impact on astronomy ([Walker et al., 2020](#)). Satellites are generally designed with reflective surfaces that can scatter sunlight towards Earth, making them appear more brightly in the sky and leading to an increase in the number of visible satellites. For observations with long exposures and/or a wide FoV, bright streaks or ‘trails’ may appear in the image as the satellite moves. This can increase noise, obscure potential targets, and hinder overall science objectives. An example of the trails left by

Figure 2.1: A wide field (2.3° across) 333 second exposure captured from the Blanco 4 m telescope at the Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory in 2019 showing several Starlink satellite streaks. Credit: CTIO/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/DECam DELVE Survey.

SpaceX Starlink satellites is shown in Figure 2.1. This 333 second exposure was captured by the Dark Energy Camera on the Victor M. Blanco Telescope in Chile, and the 19 streaks present were bright enough to be seen by the naked eye. Hence, it is clear that the presence of mega-constellations can have an adverse affect on ground-based observations.

2.1.1 Starlink

At the time of writing this thesis, SpaceX have launched almost 5000 ‘Starlink’ satellites into LEO, with current plans to extend this to 42 000 over time (McDowell, 2023). These satellites are positioned at an orbital altitude around 550 km above the Earth’s surface and are evenly distributed in orbital shells with varying inclinations, where inclination refers to the angle between a satellite’s orbit and the plane of the Earth’s equator. This strategic arrangement aims to maximize coverage and optimize the ability to deliver internet services around the globe¹. Consequently, the satellites complete an orbital period of about 90 minutes, allowing for approximately 15 orbits per day. With the significant number of Starlinks already deployed and with future plans to launch many more, this work focuses on the potential impacts of the Starlink mega-constellation in particular. Presently, the population of deployed Starlinks closely approximates the total population size over all mega-constellations in operation². Therefore, the Starlink network can be regarded as a representative sample for all mega-constellations, enabling examination of the interference on astronomy from current and future population sizes.

SpaceX was faced with immediate concerns from the astronomical community when the

¹ <https://www.starlink.com/technology>

² <https://planet4589.org/space/con/conlist.html>

Figure 2.2: Renderings of first-generation Starlinks with the original white antennas (v0.9) and the change to the DarkSat (v1.0) with the modified dark antennas (*left*), a Starlink VisorSat (v1.0) which includes a Sun visor to shade the underside of the satellite (*middle*), and a Starlink v1.5 equipped with a first-generation dielectric mirror film (*right*). Images courtesy of SpaceX.

first-generation of Starlinks were launched in 2019. Ground-based observations were reported as being polluted with satellite trails, with g – band brightness magnitudes typically ranging around 4 and 5 magnitudes (Tyson et al. 2020a; Halferty et al. 2022; Mróz et al. 2022). SpaceX had explored brightness mitigation strategies with the test launch of a single experimental ‘DarkSat’ that used a low-albedo coating to absorb light on the reflective surface of the antennae in order to reduce scattering effects (Witze, 2020). This proved effective at decreasing the reflectivity of the satellite, lowering measured g – band magnitudes to orders as low as magnitude 7 (Tregloan-Reed et al., 2020). However, this design led to thermal issues which could cause the satellite to overheat and fail, and so it was discontinued. However, SpaceX responded to the growing concerns by pledging to work with the astronomical community to help mitigate concerns about this light pollution³.

This led to the development of the ‘VisorSat’ in 2020 which included a visor that would prevent reflection by blocking sunlight from the antennas. Although these were an improvement to the original Starlinks, they were brighter than the DarkSats with a g – band brightness typically found within the 6th magnitude (Halferty et al. 2022; Mróz et al. 2022). SpaceX decided to discontinue the VisorSats after realisations that the visors generated significant drag on the satellites themselves, as well as block laser links used to expand coverage. This led to Starlink v1.5, the most recent design of the first-generation Starlinks. As an alternative to Sun visors, these use a transparent dielectric mirror film⁴ which acts to scatter most of the sunlight away from Earth, thereby reducing its brightness as observed from the ground. To the knowledge of the author, no studies have been made to measure their brightness magnitudes, despite having been launched since 2021. Image renders of the first-generation Starlink, DarkSat, and VisorSat are shown in Figure 2.2. Finally, SpaceX have helped to further mitigate concerns with the design of

³ <https://www.spacex.com/updates/#starlink-update-04-28-2020>

⁴ <https://api.starlink.com/public-files/BrightnessMitigationBestPracticesSatelliteOperators.pdf>

the second-generation Starlinks (v2.0). Although these will be significantly larger than previous Starlinks, they will improve upon v1.5 by using a second-generation dielectric film reported to reduce the observed brightness ten times better than the first-generation design⁴. While it is uncertain when these satellites will begin deployment, a smaller version called ‘v2-mini’ began launching in February 2023².

2.2 Orbital elements

Many organisations engaged in the aerospace industry maintain catalogues of space objects through the tracking of their orbits. For Earth-orbiting objects, parameters are recorded in a standardized form known as a Three-Line Element set (TLE)⁵. This data format consists of three lines of text, the first being reserved for the colloquial name of the satellite, while the second and third providing the information used to identify the spacecraft and characterize its motion. This describes the orbital elements of the satellite (i.e., the set of parameters that define the shape, orientation, and position of its orbit) at a specific point in time. Such information is necessary for predicting ephemerides⁶ of objects at a future time. TLEs are typically used to record the position and orbits of artificial satellites, allowing for the accurate tracking and prediction of their motion.

It should be noted that, TLEs are not the actual observed orbital elements of the object at the specific time, but instead are the mean elements that approximate it’s position and motion over a period of time (typically 2-3 days). They are recent enough such that we may assume that parameters like the orbital inclination, eccentricity, and the daily motion of the orbit have barely changed at the time of observation. However, finding exact representations of the true orbits is a complex task influenced by various factors including Earth’s non-uniform gravitational field, atmospheric drag, solar radiation pressure, and other perturbations (Vallado & Cefola, 2012). In particular, the Earth’s precession is a factor that must be accounted for as this will affect a satellite’s position. Since the Earth is not a perfectly symmetrical sphere, the uneven mass distribution induces a gravitational force that pulls on the Sun and moon. This causes the Earth to wobble slightly as it rotates about its axis, and thus a precession in satellite orbits (Chatters et al., 2009).

By approximating this precession, the orbital elements of the satellite at the time of observation can be estimated to a fairly high degree of accuracy. Since the TLEs are known, the value of parameters required for approximating the precession are also known, allowing for perturbation models like the Simplified General Perturbations (SGP) model to produce an orbit close to the ground-truth (Hoots & Roehrich, 1980). However, there will always be some level of uncertainty associated with TLEs and, depending on what

⁵ A TLE is referred to as a Two-Line Element set when there is no line defining the name of satellite.

⁶ An ephemeris (plural: ephemerides) is a numerical data set that describes the coordinates of celestial bodies at specific points in time, thereby providing information about their orbital parameters.

Figure 2.3: Left: The five cameras of the MASCARA system at ESO’s La Silla Observatory in Chile (Credit: J. Spronck, Leiden Observatory). Right: The housing enclosure of this MASCARA station (Credit: ESO/G. Otten and G. J. Talens).

models are used, TLEs computed by one organisation may differ from those computed by another. The North American Aerospace Defense Command (NORAD)⁷ monitors space objects and maintains one of the largest collections of TLEs computed using SGP, which are considered the standard and most widely used models within the field. These are regularly compiled, updated, and made publicly available on websites like CelesTrak⁸. SpaceX makes its Starlink ephemeris data public allowing the likes of NORAD to compute TLEs for Starlink satellites, hence NORAD TLEs are used throughout this work.

This work also makes use of the Python library Skyfield⁹, which uses SGP and other mathematical models to compute the positions and motions of stars, planets, and other celestial objects. In the context of this project, Skyfield is used to propagate orbital elements of satellites, compute the relative position of the Sun, determine transformations between different coordinate systems, and to make various astronomical calculations.

2.3 MASCARA

The Multi-site All-Sky CAmERA (MASCARA; Talens et al. 2017a) system is a wide-field imaging array consisting of two stations, one located in the Northern hemisphere (La Palma, Spain) and one in the Southern hemisphere (La Silla, Chile). This project was developed by Leiden University, along with collaboration partners like the Netherlands Research School for Astronomy (NOVA). A MASCARA station houses 5 cameras with a fixed pointing (North, South, West, East, and in the Zenith direction i.e., directly overhead) as shown in Figure 2.3. Each camera has a Field-of-View (FoV) of 53×74 degrees and a 24×36 mm Charge Coupled Device (CCD) size with $9 \mu\text{m}$ pixels. With

⁷ <https://www.norad.mil/>

⁸ <https://celestak.org/>

⁹ <https://rhodesmill.org/skyfield/>

their combined FoV, these cameras provide coverage of the near-entire sky down to 20° from the horizon. Throughout an observing night, images are captured continuously over a cadence and exposure time of approximately 6.4 sidereal¹⁰ seconds. While the station in the Northern hemisphere has been decommissioned due to operational concerns, the La Silla station in the Southern hemisphere remains operational since its first light in 2017. Each of the cameras housed in the La Silla station are indicated by the ‘LS’ identifier followed by the letter corresponding to their pointing. Hence, the 5 cameras are denoted LSN, LSS, LSW, LSE, and LSC, where C stands for center i.e., the Zenith direction. The data used throughout this work was obtained from the La Silla station, hence we will refer to the La Silla station exclusively as MASCARA from this point onward.

2.3.1 Science case

The primary purpose of MASCARA is for the observation and study of exoplanets, i.e. planets that exist outside our solar system. In particular, MASCARA operates to detect exoplanets via the transit method. As an exoplanet orbits its host star, there will be periodic instances in which it crosses, or *transits*, in front of the star as seen from the observer on Earth (Dai et al., 2021). A transiting planet will block a fraction of the light reaching the observer, resulting in a temporary reduction in the observed brightness of the star. This can be thought of as similar to the solar eclipse we experience on Earth but on much smaller scales. By measuring the total flux emitted by the star over time, one can infer the presence of an exoplanet if a periodic decrease in brightness is detected.

A light-curve is the graph obtained by plotting the amount of light measured from the star over time, an example of which is shown in Figure 2.4. The observed stellar flux will stay relatively constant when the exoplanet is not transiting, with small fluctuations due to stellar effects (Wright & Gaudi, 2013). As the exoplanet begins to cross in front of the star, the brightness will drop over the transit duration, as depicted in the Figure. If an exoplanet is truly orbiting the star, these dips in the observed brightness should therefore be periodic, enabling us to deduce its existence. It should be noted that Figure 2.4 is exaggerated for demonstration purposes and that the drop in observed brightness is extremely small in reality, reflecting the difference in size between the star and planet. The transit method not only allows for the detection of exoplanets, but also for the determination of many stellar and exoplanetary characteristics like the planet’s orbital period and size. Combining these observations with properties obtained from other detection methods allows for even more parameters to be derived (Santos et al., 2020).

Detections of transits around very bright stars can enable detailed characterizations of an exoplanet’s atmosphere, an important factor for defining a planet’s suitability in hosting life. However, these stars are sparse and observations that monitor a large area of the

¹⁰ Sidereal time measures Earth’s rotation based on the “fixed” position of the stars rather than relative to the sun. This system is useful in determining the positions of celestial objects in the sky.

Figure 2.4: An example of the transit method for detecting exoplanets. As the planet crosses in front of its host star, a dip can be found in the measured stellar flux. Periodic dips throughout time suggests the presence of an orbiting exoplanet. Image credit: NASA.

sky are therefore required to find such transits. MASCARA overcomes this challenge with its large FoV that enables it to capture all-sky observations. Moreover, MASCARA offers the capability of detecting transits through photometric measurements of stars with visual magnitude $4 < m_v < 8.4$, permitting the observation of transit events around the brightest stars in the sky. It should be noted that, at the time of its conception and construction, no other projects for finding transiting exoplanets orbiting around the brightest stars had been developed (e.g., TESS had not been launched at this time). Shortly after its first light, MASCARA discovered its first exoplanet, MASCARA-1 b, a hot Jupiter orbiting a bright $m_v = 8.3$ star (Talens et al., 2017b).

2.3.2 Data handling

A single image taken by one camera in a MASCARA system holds 22 MB of storage space. Since images are captured every 6.4 seconds, a station can produce up to 600 GB of raw data per night. Hence, it is not feasible to retain the data in its raw state and so both on-site data reduction and post-processing of images is required. The on-site reduction pipeline consists of image calibration, astrometry, and photometry to produce light curves and binned images amounting to ~ 25 Gb per night (Talens et al., 2017a). The All-Sky Compiled Catalogue (ASCC)¹¹ is used as input for the astrometry and photometry, and stars with a visual magnitude brighter than $m_v = 7$ (typically amounting to ~ 1500 stars

¹¹ <http://astro.vaporia.com/start/ascc.html>

Figure 2.5: A typical MASCARA image of the night sky taken over an exposure of 6.4 seconds.

per image) are used to find the astrometric solution¹² (Kharchenko 2001; Kharchenko et al. 2009). The astrometric solution is first updated at the beginning of the night and then after every 50th image in the exposure sequence, or after any interruptions that may occur in the process.

Image stacking and binning techniques enable the storage of fewer images while preserving the important information captured from all images. The MASCARA data-reduction pipeline stacks every 50 images to create a single binned, composite image (Talens et al., 2018). As each camera has a fixed pointing, the images must be shifted to properly align the stack in order to correct for the motion of the stars. Since the camera FoV is of considerable size, the magnitude and direction of the shift will vary across the image. To account for this, each individual image is divided into smaller tiles. The shift is then achieved by moving each tile to its position at the mid-time of the stack. This method of alignment accounts for any stellar motions that occurred during the sequence and helps create a more accurate representation of the celestial objects in the resulting composite image (Talens, 2018).

With the stars now closely aligned in each tile, the overall signal-to-noise is improved. This enhancement to the quality of the composite image enables the study of fainter objects. Once the stack is re-completed, it is divided by the total number of individual images added at each pixel. This is a normalization step to ensure that the composite image represents the average intensity over the stacked sequence. The final binned image is then compressed to further reduce storage size before finally being saved, resulting in

¹² The astrometric solution refers to the process of determining the precise positions and motions of celestial objects in the sky.

file sizes of 5 MB (~ 0.5 GB per camera per night). An example of the final image is given in Figure 2.5.

Finally, photometry is performed in order to determine the brightness of the objects within the image. Stars are selected from the ASCC catalogue and their positions are correlated to the CCD coordinates using the astrometric solution. The sky background is also estimated and subtracted from each star to account for its contribution to the total flux, ensuring a more accurate brightness measurement. These flux measurements are compiled over time to produce light curves that provide information about the time-dependent astrophysical conditions. This has a number of purposes for studying the night sky, such as tracking stellar variability, monitoring transient events, and identifying exoplanetary transits.

3 Methodology

The Feasibility study for Optical Tracking of Orbital Satellites (FOTOS) is a project supported by the Royal Netherlands Airforce (RNLAf) for the detection and classification of objects in space. It aims to create an instrument for the optical tracking and initial orbit determination of satellites in LEO. The study, along with the development of the routines, was conducted by Leiden Observatory (Wijnen et al., 2020). As the observation of satellites is an inevitable by-product of the optical wide-field MASCARA system, MASCARA data was used for the development of the methods (along with data from the bRing instrument (Stuik et al., 2017), a smaller version of MASCARA using the same software). A number of routines developed through the FOTOS study were adapted for the purpose of this thesis project, with inspiration being drawn from procedures designed for tracking and distinguishing satellites in MASCARA data. These methods were modified and extended to better align with the specific objectives of this project.

3.1 Satellite visibility

On a typical observing night, MASCARA may record approximately 25000 images between its 5 cameras. The methods for trail extraction and brightness magnitude computation (of which will be outlined in subsequent Sections) involve routines that can become computationally expensive as the number of images increase. In the context of MASCARA, running these routines on a dataset consisting of observations collected over a single night will take compute times on the order of days to over a week¹. Although this timescale is not significant enough to impede the progress of this work in any major way, it will certainly become an issue if this work is extended to multiple observing nights. In that case, compute times quickly become infeasible and it would therefore be of benefit to explore ways in which the computational expense can be reduced. One obvious approach would be to optimize the dataset such that only images are used that contain information we care about, i.e., a Starlink trail(s). For this, we must establish a means to determine whether or not a Starlink satellite will be present within a given exposure, or in other words, whether or not it will be visible relative to MASCARA.

¹ An AMD EPYC 7402P Server with ~ 100 GB of RAM was used for running the codes in this work.

A satellite’s visibility is affected by its reflectivity, which is determined by various physical properties including the material it is made from, its size, shape, and other attributes specific to its construction (Lalbakhsh et al., 2022). While these factors are important, what matters most is whether or not the satellite is illuminated by the Sun. Satellites in LEO typically do not emit any light themselves but are visible through the reflection of sunlight alone. Hence, to see a Starlink as it crosses the sky, it must be sufficiently sunlit relative to the observer. We denote the case when a Starlink will be visible as a ‘visible pass’, during which, the satellite reflects enough sunlight towards the observer to make it visible against the background of the sky.

Figure 3.1 describes the criteria for estimating the illumination of a Starlink. Firstly, the satellite must cross within the FoV of the camera. As depicted in (i), the observer at A will likely see the satellite that enters its FoV, while that at B will not as its FoV simply does not extend far enough. This can be checked by propagating the sky positions of each Starlink satellite as given by their TLEs to a given point in time, such as the time of observation. These positions can then be correlated to the pixel coordinates of each camera FoV onboard MASCARA, thereby providing a way to determine which camera, if any, should capture a passing Starlink. Taking this seemingly obvious point into account already largely reduces the number of images to use.

If the satellite is within the camera FoV, it must be sufficiently illuminated to be observable. As shown in (ii), there are three primary instances when this is not the case. At location A, the satellite is within the Earth’s shadow where no sunlight can be reached and reflected towards the observer, hence, it will not be visible. Whether or not a satellite will be within the Earth’s shadow depends on the altitude² of the Sun, as it is the Sun’s position relative to the Earth that determines the presence and location of the shadow. Hence, by computing the solar elevation for the time and location of the observation, we can determine whether or not a Starlink will be hidden in shadow. At location B, the satellite is sunlit but since it is the middle of the day relative to the observer, the sky is simply too bright and the satellite is unobservable. Again, this is determined by the solar elevation above or below the horizon.

At location C, the satellite is sufficiently sunlit but it is not high enough above the horizon relative to the observer for it to be seen. The light that is reflected off a satellite must travel through the atmosphere before it reaches the observer. The nearer a satellite is to the horizon, the more air there is between it and the observer, meaning that atmospheric effects like scattering and absorption will become more significant (Villarroel et al., 2022). This reduces the amount of reflected sunlight that reaches the observer, making it more difficult to see the satellite. The limiting conditions correspond to an altitude of around 20 to 30 degrees above the horizon. When a satellite reaches this altitude, the path length

² Note that altitude and elevation are often used interchangeably when referring to the positions of celestial objects.

Figure 3.1: Criteria to assess the visibility of a satellite in LEO. (i): the satellite must be within the camera’s FoV. (ii): The satellites at locations A and B will not be seen as they are in the middle of the night and day, respectively. The Earth’s shadow blocks any sunlight from reaching the satellite at A while the satellite at B cannot be distinguished from the brightness of the sky. The satellite at C is not high enough above the horizon relative to the observer, making it more difficult to observe as the intensity of light that reaches the observer is lessened from atmospheric effects. (iii): The green bands at locations A and B correspond to the few hours after sunset and before sunrise, the times at which a satellite is most visible provided it is sufficiently illuminated.

through the atmosphere is sufficiently minimized and atmospheric interference is reduced, improving the quality of the observation and increasing the satellite’s visibility. While a satellite may appear bright at altitudes lower than this, it is not a cause for concern as observations are generally not made this far down towards the horizon due to the higher level of attenuation making it increasingly difficult to observe astronomical sources. This is why MASCARA does not point all the way down to the horizon.

We have established that the visibility of a Starlink will decline deep into the night when it is obscured by the Earth’s shadow and during the daytime when the elevation of the Sun is high and the sky is too bright. Thus, it is the time periods between these stages when a satellite will be most visible to a ground observer, provided it is high enough above the horizon. These periods are depicted by the green bands at locations A and B in (iii), and correspond to the few hours before sunrise and after sunset, respectively. These hours coincide with the best illumination conditions of the day/night, increasing the contrast between the satellite and the sky and hence its visibility. Furthermore, just before sunrise or after sunset, the observer’s location may be in the transition zone between daylight and darkness, allowing for a better view of satellites passing through that region of the sky. This period when the atmosphere is only partially illuminated by the Sun is referred to as twilight. The degree of illumination depends on the elevation of the Sun (A_{\odot}), and it is when the Sun is around 12 to 18 degrees below the horizon (i.e., $-18^{\circ} < A_{\odot} < -12^{\circ}$) when the sky illumination becomes faint enough to best distinguish

satellites. This specific period is known as astronomical twilight, and typically begins early in the morning or ends late in the evening, with its duration depending on the time of year. As MASCARA begins its operations when the Sun reaches 10° below the horizon, most satellites should be expected to be detected towards the start and end of its nightly observations.

Thus, the solar elevation, time of observation, and satellite altitude and position are all key factors that were taken into account when developing a routine to estimate the visibility of a given Starlink. In doing so, the data was reduced to a pool of ‘quality’ images which helped in lessening the computational cost of the procedures to follow.

3.2 Recognising satellite trails

Once the visibility of Starlinks was assessed and the volume of data to be processed reduced, we now required an automated routine to search for satellite trails and make them recognisable in the data. A typical photo of the night sky will contain stars and a background that varies both in time and position. By superimposing and subtracting two consecutive images, only features that have changed between them will remain, a process we will refer to as ‘the difference of two images’ and the resulting image as the ‘delta image’. Since the position of a trail will change over time as the satellite moves across the camera’s FoV, this procedure makes it possible to distinguish any trails present in the image. The photos are superimposed such that stars are aligned to compensate for small changes in their movement due to Earth’s rotation. Hence, when the subtraction process is performed, these objects will be removed in theory and any changes between the two images will become more apparent.

An example of a resulting delta image is given in Figure 3.2. Random background noise will be retained during the difference of two images, and is conveyed here by the graininess of the image. Furthermore, increased levels of noise at the positions of particularly bright stars may become apparent, examples of which are also noticed. Satellite trails can be distinguished by a characteristic two-tone streak, highlighting the movement of the satellite over the exposure of the two images. In the subtraction process, the pixel values³ of the second image are subtracted from those in the first. As the pixels belonging to a trail will generally be of a higher intensity compared to the surrounding background, subtracting these values from a region of the image without a trail will drop the pixel values within that region below zero. Hence, the two-tone nature of a satellite trail corresponds to positive and negative pixel values, where the negative values arise from subtracting the pixel values from the position of the trail in the second image. In the Figure, this is demonstrated by two satellite trails that are clearly seen in the left portion of the image. In this case, the white segment of the trail coincides with positive pixel

³ Pixel value refers to the number of light particles that fell on a given pixel during the shutter speed.

Figure 3.2: The delta image resulting from the difference of two images process in which two successive images are superimposed and subtracted from each other. The choice of image colormap was done so to increase the contrast between the features and background.

values (i.e., the pixel values belonging to the position of the trail in the first image), while the darker segment corresponds to negative pixel values, indicating the position of the trail in the second image at a further point in time.

It can be noted that other, shorter satellite trails are evident in the delta image. These correspond to satellites in orbits higher than LEO, where the movement of a satellite over the two exposures appears slower due to its greater orbital distance. Other features can be further noted, such as the dark long streak in the center-right portion of the image. Because of its length and single-tone nature, it can be inferred that this trail likely belongs to a meteor. The particularly long length of the trail is explained by the fast speeds at which these objects travel, and since it is only picked up in the second image, it likely burned up (thereby making it luminous) or dissipated in this exposure only.

3.3 Extracting satellite trails

After satellite trails are made recognisable, there is still the challenge of separating and extracting them from the rest of the image for further analysis. This is required to isolate the information we care about, such as the pixels only belonging to trails. Before this, we firstly employ noise reduction techniques to increase the contrast between the trail and background. This helps to amplify the differences in pixel values, allowing subsequent routines to then better distinguish the trail from the background.

3.3.1 Suppressing noise

The random variation of pixel values means that digital images will always have some level of random noise present. This will manifest as small speckles on the image, making it appear more grainy and affecting its quality and clarity. Since this noise is inherently random, it will carry over when creating a delta image, leading to an increased level of noise. Generally, there are two dominant components to this random noise; readout noise and photon noise. Readout noise occurs when the electrical charge in each pixel of the CCD sensor is converted into a digital signal. It is typically characterized as the magnitude of the fluctuations in the pixel values, and is independent of the light falling on those pixels. Photon noise (or shot noise) refers to the random variation in the number of photons detected by the detector per unit time. This is due to the probabilistic nature of light which causes the photons to arrive at random intervals, leading to an inherently random variation of pixel values. It is dependent on the number of photons, n , falling on a pixel, and its magnitude is characterized by \sqrt{n} . This means that bright stars can still be visible in a delta image, where the pixel value remaining is of the order \sqrt{n} .

For each delta image, noise reduction techniques were employed to suppress the impact of random noise and increase the overall signal-to-noise ratio. Let us consider the example of the delta image given in Figure 3.3a, where a number of satellite trails of varying intensity can be seen. Firstly, the absolute value of the delta image is taken to ensure that the changes between the two images are of the same sign (this is necessary for comparing the magnitudes of each pixel value), as shown in Figure 3.3b. It can be noted that a correlated noise pattern becomes apparent when the absolute value of the delta image is taken. This is partly due to non-uniformities in the response of individual pixels as a result of the inherent characteristics of the CCD itself. These pixel-to-pixel variations can manifest as a fixed noise pattern across the image and lead to distinct and consistent artifacts including dark or bright spots, stripes, or grid-like patterns. The deviations caused by a fixed noise pattern become more pronounced when taking the absolute value of the image since they are no longer balanced out by deviations of the opposite sign.

Following this, noise from bright stars is accounted for through masking, the result of which is given in Figure 3.3c. Since the positions of these stars are known, it is possible to replace (i.e., mask) those pixels with a different value. This is done with the median pixel value of the entire delta image so that the background characteristics are preserved and a statistical consistency within the image is ensured. It is worth noting that it is possible that a satellite trail will cross over stars that have been masked out through this process, with an example of this evident in Figure 3.3c. In this case, there will be gaps in the trail that may interfere with the subsequent routines for trail extraction and analysis, as will be further discussed in Section 3.3.2.

The remaining random noise occurring in all pixels is dealt with by increasing the contrast

(a) A delta image with satellite trails present.

(b) Result from taking the absolute value of (a).

(c) Bright stars are masked out from (b) with the median pixel value of (a).

(d) Random noise in (c) is suppressed and a reduced image is made.

Figure 3.3: The process of applying noise reduction techniques to a delta image for creating a reduced image with enhanced contrast between the trail and background.

between the satellite trails and background. As a trail will have a finite width and length, certain operations can be used to distinguish it from the randomly distributed noise. Following the routine outlined by [Rood \(2021\)](#), this is achieved by looking at the intensity of the pixel values throughout the image. Firstly, a binary image is created by setting all pixel values that are more than 1 standard deviation (σ) above the mean to value 1, and the rest to value 0. Pixels belonging to a trail are then defined as having values 2.5σ above the mean, as well as having at least six neighbouring pixels with values 1σ above the mean. Pixels that do not meet this criteria are replaced with the mean value, thereby suppressing noise while retaining any trails. To further enhance the contrast between trail and background, a so-called ‘reduced image’ is then created by setting each pixel to a value of either 0 or 1 depending on the signal strength. The result of these noise reduction techniques is given in [Figure 3.3d](#).

It can be noted that some trails are not fully distinguished or distinguished at all when compared to the initial delta image in [Figure 3.3a](#). This is because of the varying intensity of the trails as measured by the CCD, with some trails appearing much brighter

than others. Fainter trails will be more affected by the operations used for noise suppression, simply due to it being more challenging to distinguish pixels of a lower intensity from the background noise. Hence, there is a detection limit that is determined by the signal-to-noise ratio between the satellite trail and background. This means that these techniques are not perfect and there exists the possibility of losing information we care about. Although trails of a relatively low intensity can be considered as unimportant to this study, analysis of them could provide insight into the relationships between a satellite’s brightness and orbital parameters. Furthermore, this prompts the question of whether the intensity given by the measurement is physically sound or if it is in fact due to the detection limit.

3.3.2 Line detection

To extract trails from the background, we use the fact that they will appear to be approximately linear. With the contrast between trail and background now enhanced, it should be easier to distinguish and isolate line segments in the image that belong to satellite trails. Hence, line detection methods are implemented to automate the distinction of trails and select their pixel values. Two techniques commonly used within the field are utilized: the Hough Transform (HT) and the Random Sample Consensus (RANSAC) method. The HT is a feature extraction tool that is used here to determine the positions of any line segments it can find within an image, while the RANSAC method is then used to improve these initial line detections. Further procedures are also implemented to refine these detections and better match them to any satellite trails present.

With the reduced image as input, the HT begins by examining all positive pixels in this binary image. A line is then extended through each pixel with an angle that is free to vary to allow for flexibility in detecting different trail segment orientations. For each line drawn, the algorithm searches for the largest number of pixels that align with it in terms of their position and orientation. It does this by looking for pixels that have an angle and perpendicular distance which matches the line drawn through the pixel. These matching pixels are considered to potentially lie on a trail segment, where the more pixels that match the segment, the higher the likelihood that it exists in the image. Following this, the intensities of the pixels that lie on each line are examined in order to better determine whether or not the segment could belong to a satellite trail. Parameters such as the line length and continuity are also considered such that the lines must meet a specified minimum length and not have gaps larger than a threshold number of pixels.

Although this method is effective in detecting lines, it does not provide a conclusive determination of whether a detected line segment represents the entire satellite trail or if it should be considered as part of another line. As a result, the HT will sometimes fit multiple lines to a single trail. This is a problem as we want to approximate a satellite trail by a single line defined by a start- and end- point. Note that the start-point is defined

Figure 3.4: Line detection methods: (a) shows a portion of a reduced image containing a single trail. (b) gives the result of applying the Hough Transform to (a). The initial routines for merging and connecting lines are then applied to obtain the lines in (c).

by the position of the satellite when it ‘enters’ the first image (of the two used in creating the delta image), while the end-point is given by the position in which the satellite ‘exits’ the second image. We will refer to these simply as the end-points. To address this issue, additional routines are implemented to merge and connect lines together based on their positions. Firstly, line segments are merged into a single line if their end-points are within a specified threshold number of pixels from each other. In this process, the resulting line retains the outermost end-points from the original segments. We then inspect if line segments align with each other to infer if they should be connected. If aligned, we again check if their end-points are within a threshold distance to each other, connecting the lines into a single segment if so. This also helps to fill in any gaps in the trail that may have resulted from the masking of bright stars in the image.

Figure 3.4a gives an example of a single satellite trail in a reduced image. After applying the HT to this, 10 lines were found, as shown in 3.4b. Following this, the routines to merge and connect lines were applied, reducing them to the 3 seen in 3.4c. As can be observed, these methods are not perfect, with some lines incomplete and not fully combined. We have inferred that this is mainly due to the threshold parameters for combining lines, where constant values are used. The values chosen were motivated by the similarities of trails belonging to satellites in LEO. While this is a reasonable approximation, it begins to break down if gaps in the lines from random noise and the masking of stars are prominent. A refined routine that treats these parameters in an adaptive way may be better appropriate, but an approach like this would be much more involved. However, as will be discussed further below, a simpler solution to this issue was found.

The RANSAC method is the next tool employed in the line detection procedure. We use this to improve upon the detections made by the HT, mainly in refining the orientation of a detected line. This iterative algorithm works by randomly sampling subsets of the

Figure 3.5: Additional methods for line detection: (a) gives the result of applying the RANSAC method to Figure 3.4c. Next, lines for a given satellite are distinguished as lying within the ellipse shown in (b), where the green markers give the TLE positions of the trail. With this information, a single line that best represents the full satellite trail can then be found, as shown in (c).

detected line segments and fitting them to a line model. By estimating the best-fitting model, the slope, and hence the orientation of the line, can be approximated. Following this, the end-points of each fitted line segment is then determined. This is achieved by comparing the line segments with the original delta image. By overlaying the lines on the delta image, we can determine the pixels of the delta image that belong to a given segment. Since there may be inconsistencies and gaps in the continuity of the line due to random noise and background stars, an optimization function is then used to determine the ‘true’ length of the line segment.

The result of applying the RANSAC method and end-point determination routine to our example is given in Figure 3.5a. The lines have been successfully orientated and extended to fill in the gaps and better approximate the trail, but because 3 lines were given by the previous routine, we are still left with 3 separate lines rather than the one continuous segment we wish to obtain. Our solution to remedy this is as follows. Firstly, we identify the satellites that are present in the image and correlate their positions (as determined from their orbital elements) to the pixel coordinates of the delta image. Next, on a satellite-by-satellite basis, we use the end-points as given by the orbital elements to draw an ellipse around the trail. This is shown in 3.5b, where the green markers correspond to the end-points from the orbital elements. Due to offsets resulting from the difference of two images process, these points may not align with the start- and end-points shown in the delta image, which explains why this is the case in our example here. Therefore, certain characteristics of the trail, such as its position and length, may differ between those given by the delta image and the orbital elements. For simplicity, we will distinguish between delta image properties and TLE properties, where TLE properties refer to those given by the orbital elements (i.e., as published by their TLE).

The orientation and size of the ellipse is defined by the TLE properties, and so is unique to the given trail. As there may be other lines detected throughout the image, we use this ellipse to identify which lines ‘belong’ to the given satellite by only selecting the lines that lie within it. We then determine which portions of the lines belong to the first segment of the trail (i.e., from the first image) and which belong to the second segment (i.e., from the second image). This allows us to identify which points coincide with the start- and end- points of the trail. Finally, we draw a line connecting these points to attain a single line that represents the full satellite trail. Continuing with our example, this is shown in Figure 3.5c by the dotted line. We see that it aligns well with the trail as given in the reduced image and that the end-points, as conveyed by the white crosses, adequately fit the beginning and end of the trail. With these line detection procedures, we now have a means to identify and extract the pixels within a delta image belonging to trails.

3.4 Brightness magnitudes

The visual brightness magnitude of a satellite provides a quantitative measure of its visibility in the v – band, and hence can be a useful way to characterize its impact on ground-based optical astronomy. Satellites with high brightness magnitudes⁴ are more likely to be visible in observations and therefore potentially interfere with scientific research. Hence, the cataloguing of satellite brightness magnitudes (or simply, magnitudes) is a primary objective of this work. For this, we make use of existing routines from the FOTOS study which determines the magnitude of a satellite by comparing it with the brightness of the surrounding stars.

The actual brightness of a satellite depends on a number of physical factors including its reflectivity, size, and orientation. On the other hand, the intensity of the satellite trail as given by the CCD depends on the sensitivity of the camera. Due to electronic variations in the detector, a camera’s sensitivity may vary across its FoV. Therefore, a trail’s observed intensity will depend on the sensitivity of the camera at the specific position where the trail appears (i.e., the *local* sensitivity at the position of the trail on the CCD). For a given trail, the local sensitivity must be calibrated, which can be achieved by examining the local brightness of the background and surrounding stars. A star’s brightness is dependent on its flux, F , and can be expressed in terms of visual magnitudes, m_v , through the following relationship:

$$m_v = -2.5 \log_{10}(F) + C \tag{3.1}$$

⁴ It should be noted that brightness magnitudes are given on a logarithmic scale, hence high brightness magnitude are given by lower numbers compared to fainter objects. An object around magnitude 4-5 can be visible to the naked eye, while Pluto has a magnitude around 14. It should also be noted that these refer to apparent magnitudes and do not characterize an object’s intrinsic luminosity.

Figure 3.6: Computing a trail’s brightness magnitude: A cigar-like region containing the satellite trail is selected in (a). The average value of the local background is then determined from the donut shaped region around the trail shown in (b). Per pixel, this is subtracted from the region in (a) to remove the background contribution. Stars within a circle centered on the middle of the trail with radius equal to the trail’s length are then selected as reference to use in Equation 3.1. This is depicted by the grey markers in (c).

where C is a constant. The flux can be approximated by counting the number of photons captured by the CCD while the magnitude of known stars in the sky are catalogued and readily available (e.g., through the Gaia⁵ archive). Hence, the constant C can be determined and, by then measuring the flux of the satellite, the magnitude of the trail computed using the relation from Equation 3.1. In this way, C serves as a correction factor that accounts for any calibration offsets or systematic differences between the instrumental measurements (i.e., the fluxes) and the known magnitudes of stars. As will be discussed in Section 5.1, these offsets can arise due to various factors related to the environmental conditions, instrument response, or data processing techniques. The inclusion of C corrects for these offsets when converting the measured instrumental flux into the more meaningful physical unit of brightness magnitudes. Hence, we will refer to C as the calibration constant.

Continuing from the reduced delta image in Figure 3.5c, this process can be achieved through the following. Firstly, we determine the flux of the satellite trail. We want to ensure that background photons are not counted towards the trail, so we start by separating the region containing the trail from the surrounding sky background. We define the region containing the trail by selecting the pixels within a cigar-like shape around it, as shown in Figure 3.6a. To remove the background contribution from this region, we subtract the typical background value from each pixel. However, since the background may vary in position across the CCD, we use the average value of the *local* background. We define the local region coinciding with this by selecting the pixels that lie within a donut shaped area around the cigar, as depicted in Figure 3.6b. The mean value

⁵ <https://gea.esac.esa.int/archive/>

Figure 3.7: An example of the derived magnitude-flux relation for a region of the sky containing a satellite trail. The linear fit is used to estimate the calibration constant, allowing for the magnitude of the trail to be determined (as shown by the red marker). The ADU unit for flux measures the digital value representing the intensity of light recorded by the pixels in the CCD.

of those pixels are then subtracted from the pixels within the cigar, thereby eliminating the contribution of background photons to the trail. With only the signal from the trail retained, we sum over these pixels to calculate the flux of the trail.

We now want to convert this flux measurement into a brightness magnitude. For this, we must identify the stars that are in close proximity to the trail to use as reference. These are defined by those that lie within a circle centered on the middle of the trail with radius equal to the trail’s length. The grey markers in Figure 3.6c convey the reference stars that are within this region. The magnitude of these stars are catalogued and their flux values have already been determined from the standard data reduction process. Hence, we can now estimate the calibration constant from Equation 3.1 by performing a linear fit to a plot of the nearby stellar magnitudes as a function of CCD flux values.

Figure 3.7 demonstrates the resulting magnitude-flux relation for this particular region, where the visual magnitudes (m_v) and fluxes of the reference stars are plotted. The black line represents the line-of-best-fit from fitting Equation 3.1 to this scatter. This allows us to estimate the value of the calibration constant, for which we then use to derive the visual magnitude of the satellite trail. The red marker illustrates this value, which was approximated as 4.9 ± 0.05 (the determination of the uncertainty measurement will be discussed in Section 3.5). The processes outlined here are repeated for each trail that is successfully extracted from the delta image.

3.5 Error propagation

To estimate the uncertainty on the measured brightness magnitude for a satellite trail, we consider the dominant sources of error present in Equation 3.1. There are two components to this; the error associated with the flux measurement, and the error associated with the calibration constant. Hence, we want to calculate the uncertainty for a quantity that depends on two variables. We can therefore use the general formula for error propagation:

$$\sigma_m = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\delta m}{\delta F} \cdot \sigma_F\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\delta m}{\delta C} \cdot \sigma_C\right)^2} \quad (3.2)$$

where $\delta m/\delta F$ and $\delta m/\delta C$ are the partial derivatives of the magnitude with respect to the flux and calibration constant, respectively, σ_F and σ_C are the uncertainties associated with the flux and calibration constant, respectively, and σ_m is the quantity we wish to estimate, i.e., the uncertainty associated with the magnitude of the satellite trail. Since F and C will both be known, the partial derivatives can be simply computed. Since C is estimated through curve fitting, it is also straight forward to find σ_C . When fitting the linear relation given by Equation 3.1, we obtain the optimized value of the fit parameter, C , along with its estimated variance. By taking the square root of the variance, we find the standard deviation associated with C , which we use as a more intuitive representation of σ_C (compared to the variance).

Estimating a value for σ_F requires a more involved approach. With an exposure time around 6.4 seconds, a satellite in LEO will take up-to two minutes to cross the FoV of a MASCARA camera. We will refer to this as a ‘pass-by’. Over this short time duration, we expect the measured flux of its trail and hence, its brightness magnitude, to remain relatively constant or changing uniformly. Therefore, on a single satellite basis, we expect to find an approximately linear trend on the measured flux as a function of time. If so, we can apply a linear fit to the data and look at the residuals, i.e., the differences between the measured data points and the corresponding values predicted by the linear model. The uncertainty can then be quantified by computing the Root Mean Square (RMS) value, which defines how well the fitted model describes the observed data. This is achieved by calculating the mean of the squared residuals and taking its square root.

However, the uniformity of the measured flux values during a pass-by will depend on the position of the satellite on the CCD as well as the effectiveness of the routines for extracting its trail from the data. As discussed in Section 3.3.1, the sensitivity of the CCD varies across the FoV of the camera, meaning that the measured flux will depend on the local sensitivity at the specific position of the satellite. Although this may cause the measured flux to deviate from uniformity, the fluctuations are small enough such that a linear trend is still to be expected and applying a linear fit would remain valid. However,

it is possible that the routines for trail extraction only manage to extract a portion of the trail rather than the full segment. This may occur if the contrast between the trail and background is not sufficiently high enough causing the line detection algorithms to fail in distinguishing the full trail. In this case, the measured flux will be lower than it should be, since it is being calculated for only a fraction of the trail. Hence, the measured flux of a single satellite trail during a pass-by may not stay constant as a function of time, and applying a linear fit to the data would no longer be appropriate.

However, we can choose to treat instances where the trail is not adequately extracted as outliers. By removing these outliers, we ensure that the flux measurements are of sufficient quality in that a linear trend as a function of time can be expected. We create this subset by accepting measurements that are within 10% of the trail’s TLE length (i.e., with a length equal to at least 90% or at most 110% of the TLE length). Allowing for lengths within this range also accounts for any deviations in the measurement due to the local sensitivity of the CCD. Furthermore, to establish a linear fit of sufficient reliability, a minimum of 5 data points is required. There will be pass-bys for which not enough measurements were successfully made to meet this condition, due to a limited time spent within the camera’s FoV or from a failure to detect and extract the trail from the background. Hence, per camera, we further limit the data to satellites that were detected at least 5 times during a pass-by.

After applying these sample statistics, the data was reduced to 39 different satellites with a total of 283 measurements. With this sigma-clipped subset, we apply a linear trend to the measured flux values for each pass-by and compute the corresponding RMS value (normalized to the specific range of data used). These RMS values quantify the spread of residuals for each fit and provide an estimate of the typical magnitude of the measurement errors. By taking the standard deviation of these RMS values, we attain an indication of the variability of uncertainties across the different fits. This provides a single value that characterizes the average deviation or uncertainty in the different flux measurements. Although this provides an overestimation of the actual RMS error, it serves as a first-order estimation of the overall uncertainty on the flux.

Figure 3.8 illustrates an example of the procedures outlined for a single Starlink satellite during a pass-by. The blue and orange curves give the trail length as derived from the TLE and delta image, respectively, while the red curve indicates the measured flux. The fluctuation in the uniformity of the flux is likely attributed to the local sensitivity of the CCD, where the jump in magnitude conveys a region of the sensor with higher sensitivity and hence a higher than average transmission. For this pass-by, 8 observations were successfully recorded, where each data point corresponds to a single observation. The grid lines are spaced by the exposure time of the camera to better apprehend the time-sequence depicted. The dashed black line shows the linear fit to the trail flux which gives a normalized RMS value of 0.08, indicating quite a good fit. This was carried out for

Figure 3.8: The trail length (*left-axis*) and flux (*right-axis*) for the STARLINK-1073 satellite as a function of time during a pass-by. Each data point corresponds to a single observation, and the grid lines are separated by the ~ 6.4 s exposure time of the camera. The dashed black line shows the linear fit to the trail flux, which gives a normalized RMS value of 0.08.

the remaining pass-bys in the subset and the standard deviation of all RMS values was found. By following this procedure, we estimate a value of σ_F and thereby use Equation 3.2 to approximate the uncertainty on the measured brightness magnitude for a given satellite trail.

4 Results

Data was collected for a single observing night on 24th October 2022 over an almost 9 hour period between 00:23 - 09:02. At this time, 3173 Starlink satellites had been launched into orbit. In total, 23060 observations were captured between each of the 5 MASCARA cameras. From this, 21990 delta images could be made. After applying the routines outlined in Section 3.1 for assessing the illumination of a satellite, the data was reduced to a subset of 3019 images estimated to contain visible Starlinks within the FoV. Of this, Starlink trails were successfully found and extracted for 1282 images, amounting to a total of 1605 separate measurements for 175 unique Starlink satellites. These figures are summarized in Table 4.1. The reason why Starlink trails were not extracted for 1737 of the images within our reduced subset is discussed in Section 5.2.1.

For each of the 1605 trails detected, information about the particular measurement was catalogued. This included properties related to the satellite and the conditions of its orbit so that a more in-depth analysis of the difference in Starlinks observed could be carried out. Relevant orbital parameters that are not found in the TLEs were determined through SGP models using the Skyfield library. An example of the type of information that was recorded is presented in Table A1.

Table 4.1: A summary of the MASCARA data collected and reduced for the night of observations. Per camera, N delta images gives the number of delta images that were created, N usable images gives the number of images with visible and extracted Starlink trails, and N detections gives the total number of Starlinks detected among the usable images. For the 1605 measurements made, a total of 175 unique Starlink satellites were observed.

Camera	N delta images	N usable images	N detections
LSN	4398	90	109
LSS	4398	377	450
LSW	4398	366	457
LSE	4398	300	422
LSC	4398	149	167
Total	21990	1282	1605

Figure 4.1: Histograms of the visual brightness magnitudes (*left*) and their uncertainties (*right*) computed for 1605 measurements of Starlink trails. The purple line represents the average magnitude over all observations (5.3 ± 0.1).

4.1 Photometric study

Following the procedures outlined in Sections 3.4 - 3.5, brightness magnitudes and their corresponding uncertainties were computed for each detected trail. The distributions of these measurements are represented by the histograms in Figure 4.1. The average value of the magnitude over all measurements is indicated by the purple line, for which a value of $\langle m_v \rangle = 5.3 \pm 0.1$ was found. It can be noted that a large number of these magnitudes reach values that can be visible to the naked eye, with the brightest magnitude measured to be $m_v = 1.7 \pm 0.04$. Although the significant brightness of this measurement questions its validity, the trail was found to be correctly identified and its brightness computed accordingly (see Appendix B for further details).

It can become problematic to directly compare the measured magnitude values due to the different ranges recorded for each satellite. By range, we refer to the distance between the satellite and observer (i.e., MASCARA) at the time of observation. While Starlinks orbit at a nominal altitude of around 550 km, the range between a Starlink and the observer will exceed this value when not passing directly overhead (i.e., at Zenith). In fact, the ranges recorded among all observations varied between 546 - 1281 km, with a median value of about 784 km. Hence, to facilitate an easier comparison and analysis of the magnitudes measured across the different observations, the magnitudes were scaled to a common range of 1000 km. This form of standardization is commonly used within the field, thereby enabling consistent comparisons with other studies. The scaling factor adopted corresponds to the inverse square law of light and takes the form:

$$m_{\text{norm}} = m_{\text{obs}} - 5 \log(r/1000 \text{ km}) \quad (4.1)$$

Figure 4.2: Histogram of the 1605 measured brightness magnitudes normalized to a common range of 1000 km. Lines are drawn to represent the average magnitudes for the different types of Starlink satellites: dotted green gives that for Standard Starlinks (5.9 ± 0.09), dashed orange gives that for the VisorSats (5.6 ± 0.1), dashed-dotted red gives that for the DarkSats (6.6 ± 0.09), and solid purple gives that for all observations (5.8 ± 0.1).

where m_{obs} is the observed brightness magnitude of the satellite trail, r is its observed range in km, and m_{norm} is the new value of its brightness magnitude which has been normalized to a standard distance of 1000 km. The distribution of these ‘range normalized’ magnitudes is shown by the histogram in Figure 4.2. We see that the overall average magnitude, as given by the solid purple line, is now fainter than before, with a value $\langle m_v \rangle = 5.8 \pm 0.1$. It is noted that this is with a standard deviation of 0.95. Lines to depict the average magnitudes determined for the different types of Starlink satellites are also plotted. The average magnitude for Standard Starlinks (i.e., those that are not VisorSats or DarkSats) is given by the dotted green line (5.9 ± 0.09), that for the VisorSats is given by the dashed orange line (5.6 ± 0.1), and that for the DarkSats is given by the dashed-dotted red line (6.6 ± 0.09).

We see that the average brightness magnitude is faintest for the DarkSats, as expected. However, while it is noted that just one DarkSat exists, only two measurements of it were made. Hence, data collected over additional observing nights would be required to make a more reliable photometric comparison with other Starlinks. Interestingly, the average magnitude for the VisorSat was found to be lower than that for the Standard design. However, we categorize the Standard Starlinks as those that are neither VisorSats nor DarkSats. Therefore, satellite designs post VisorSat that are potentially better at reducing their reflectance are included in our ‘Standard’ definition.

Figure 4.3: Histogram of the range normalized brightness magnitudes with the observed Starlinks distinguished by their version number. The red, orange, and blue bars represent the v0.9, v1.0, and v1.5 Starlinks, respectively. Their respective average magnitudes is given by the legend (6.0 ± 0.1 , 5.7 ± 0.1 , and 5.9 ± 0.09)

To better explore this, we distinguish between the different Starlink versions (v0.9, v1.0, v1.5) as defined in Section 2.1.1. The reader is reminded that v0.9 specifies the initially deployed Starlinks before brightness mitigations were taken, v1.0 refers to first-generation Starlinks that included modifications to their design (e.g., DarkSat and VisorSats), and v1.5 Starlinks define those that were designed post-VisorSat with a dielectric mirror film to further reduce their reflectance. A histogram of the measured brightness magnitudes for these sub-groups is shown in Figure 4.3. The average magnitudes for each version as given by the legend confirms our previous speculation about VisorSats being of a lower magnitude on average when compared to the Standard Starlinks. Interestingly, v0.9 Starlinks are found to be faintest on average (6.0 ± 0.1), whereas v1.0 are brightest (5.7 ± 0.1), suggesting that the mitigations taken to reduce the reflectance in v1.0 Starlinks were ineffective. Compared to v1.0, the introduction of the dielectric mirror film seemed to help reduce the brightness of the v1.5 Starlinks, although, with $\langle m_v \rangle = 5.9 \pm 0.09$, it is still slightly brighter on average than v0.9. However, it is noted that of the 1605 observations made, 667 were v1.5, 814 were v1.0, but only 124 were for v0.9.

One of the recommendations of the Satellite Constellations 1 (SATCON1) workshop which helped to quantify the impacts of mega-constellations on astronomy, was that the satellites should be fainter than $m_v = 7$ (Walker et al., 2020). It is noted that all of the average magnitudes reported here are brighter than this limit, and that approximately 95% of all measurements do not meet this recommendation. Thus, up-to the time of observation, none of the mitigation strategies adopted by SpaceX have been sufficient

Table 4.2: A comparison of Starlink trail visual magnitudes (normalized to a common range of 1000 km) reported from different studies.

Paper	Standard	VisorSat	DarkSat	v0.9	v1.0	v1.5
This work (2023)	5.9 ± 0.09	5.6 ± 0.10	6.6 ± 0.09	6.0 ± 0.1	5.7 ± 0.1	5.9 ± 0.09
Halferty et al. (2022)	-	6.2 ± 0.89	7.5 ± 0.88	-	5.3 ± 1.2	-
Johnson et al. (2021)	6.9 ± 0.9	6.8 ± 1.1	6.77 ± 1.19	-	-	-
Mallama (2020)	5.93 ± 0.02	7.18 ± 0.03	-	-	-	-

enough to reach the target set by the SATCON1 workshop.

The normalization scheme applied allows for a more meaningful comparison to similar studies that also standardized the measured magnitudes to a common range of 1000 km. This is given in Table 4.2. Most of the studies included here focused on the differences between DarkSat, VisorSat, and v1.0 Starlinks. Some agreement is seen throughout the different studies. Our figures fall into the uncertainty range given by the average reported magnitudes of [Halferty et al. \(2022\)](#), which consisted of a smaller sample size of 353 observations. Although it is a poorer agreement, our figures also compare to those given by [Johnson et al. \(2021\)](#) for which 2170 observations were made. Finally, our result for the average magnitude of Standard Starlinks agrees best with that reported by [Mallama \(2020\)](#), for which 830 observations were made. To the knowledge of the author, our study is the first to include observations of v1.5 Starlinks.

4.2 Geometric study

To further inspect the distribution of brightness magnitudes computed for each Starlink observation, we explore certain geometric properties. As outlined in Section 3.1, we expect to detect Starlinks at certain times of the night - in the few hours after and before sunset and sunrise, respectively. Since the altitude of the Sun and satellite are both properties that affect how illuminated a satellite is relative to the ground observer, we should expect to see trends in the distribution of their measurements that coincide with the frequency of satellite observations.

This is depicted by Figure 4.4 which shows three plots as a function of time during the observing hours of the night; the altitude A of the satellite (*top-panel*), a histogram of Starlink detections (*middle-panel*), and the altitude A_{\odot} of the Sun (*bottom-panel*). The beginning and end of the night is defined by the observing conditions which are assessed by MASCARA to determine when it's enclosure should be opened and closed. As expected, Starlink observations were only made during a short time-period after sunset and leading up-to sunrise, leaving a gap of almost 6 hours during the middle of the night where no satellites were observed. Hence, the x -axis of each plot is broken into two separate time-ranges that correspond to the periods of the night when detections were made, thereby

Figure 4.4: The altitude A of the satellite (*top-panel*), a histogram of Starlink detections (*middle-panel*), and the altitude A_{\odot} of the Sun (*bottom-panel*), all as a function of time during the observing hours of the night of observations. An almost 6 hour gap when no satellite detections were made is omitted by breaking the x -axes into two. The histogram is weighted by the magnitudes computed for each detection, as given by the legend.

removing the ~ 6 hour gap for a visually simpler inspection. The lower frequency of detections at the tail ends of this gap is best demonstrated by the histogram, where we see a gradual decrease just after sunset, and a gradual increase just before sunrise. To investigate if brighter magnitudes are found at certain times of the night, the histogram is weighted by the magnitudes computed for each detection as given by the legend, although no clear correlation is seen.

To better evaluate why we see a gradual decrease and subsequent increase in detections at the beginning and end of the night, respectively, we look to the distribution of solar altitudes. As discussed in Section 3.1, satellites are expected to be most visible during twilight hours. In particular, the best visibility conditions coincide with astronomical twilight when the Sun is at an altitude between 12 and 18 degrees below the horizon (i.e., $-18^{\circ} < A_{\odot} < -12^{\circ}$). As the Sun drops further below, we should expect the illumination levels to decrease and less detections to be made. This concurs with our histogram of satellite detections. At the start of the night, observations begin at $A_{\odot} = -18^{\circ}$. The detection frequency is highest here as this period falls within astronomical twilight, during which illumination conditions for satellites are best. However, this point marks its ending and the visibility will therefore diminish as the evening transitions fully into night. As A_{\odot}

decreases, the detection frequency declines towards zero at 01:45, marking the beginning of the deep-night when satellites become completely hidden within the Earth’s shadow.

The illumination conditions begin to then improve as A_{\odot} increases during the few hours before sunrise. This is seen around a time of 07:30, where the frequency of detections starts to increase as the Sun gradually rises higher into the sky. Detections are then highest when astronomical twilight is reached once again at $A_{\odot} = -18^{\circ}$. Beyond this point, the sky gets increasingly bright and adequate observations become more difficult to make, hence MASCARA is closed and the observing night ends. It is noted that MASCARA may begin/end observations at a solar elevation of -10° . However, satellites were only searched for when the Sun was 18° or lower below the horizon, as satellite detections made under this condition are regarded as having the ability to disrupt science objectives in a more significant way (since astronomical sources are generally not observed at solar elevations higher than this).

Finally, the distribution of satellite altitudes further agrees with our understanding of the illumination conditions during these hours. As expected, detections of satellites at a higher altitude are more frequent at the tail ends of the night. The illumination conditions are optimal during these hours, whereas satellites at higher altitudes are less likely to be detected at times between these due to a greater influence of atmospheric distortion. It is noted that, as MASCARA points down to 20° above the horizon, no detections of satellites below this altitude were made.

4.3 Science interference

To better characterize the level at which MASCARA observations were impacted by Starlink trails, we look at how potential science objectives may be disturbed by estimating how many stars were affected. This can be achieved by approximating how much of the FoV for each camera was affected per observation (i.e., per delta image). A trail may pass over a number of stars which will both obscure them and affect their measured brightness. It should be noted that the size of the area obscured by a trail will depend on its length as detected by the CCD. Although these satellites all orbit at approximately the same height, the length is not a constant but will depend on geometric properties such as altitude and distance from the observer. Furthermore, as described in Section 3.5, the routines for trail extraction may not entirely capture the true length, which may lead to an underestimation of the area affected. Hence, the following methods are approximative and depend on the particular observation.

Due to the sensitivity of the CCD, the intensity of pixels belonging to a trail may bleed into nearby pixels surrounding it, thereby affecting those pixel values. Therefore, it is not sufficient to only look at the pixels belonging to a trail to estimate the percentage of the FoV affected, and instead we must define a region surrounding the trail. As described in

Section 3.4, the region containing a trail is defined by the pixels within a cigar-like shape around it (i.e., the annulus used for measuring the flux of the trail). This encompasses a region of 20 pixels wide in each direction from the trail, where we assume the pixels within this region to be under the influence of the trail (i.e., we assume the trail pixel intensities may affect the flux values measured for the objects within this region). The area of this region is then determined to approximate how much of the camera’s FoV is covered by that particular trail. This is done for any other trails in the image and the percentage of the FoV that is obscured by trails is calculated to estimate the extent at which the given observation is affected.

This process was carried out for each of the 1282 delta images, the results of which are given in Figure 4.5. Each bar chart shows the percentage of the camera FoV that has been affected by Starlink trails as a function of time during the night of observations, where a single bar corresponds to a single observation (i.e., a delta image). Each plot represents one of the 5 MASCARA cameras as indicated by the legend labels (where LSN, LSS, LSW, LSE, and LSC denote the North, South, West, East, and Zenith camera pointings, respectively). Again, a break in the x -axis is done to omit the ~ 6 hour gap during the middle of the night when no satellite detections were made.

It is worth noting that the difference in the frequency of detections between each camera is explained by their particular pointing. This is best exemplified by comparing the Westward and Eastward cameras. At the beginning of the night, the Western horizon is more visible compared to that of the East. Since the Sun sets in the West, the sky will darken as it transitions from daylight to nighttime, thereby improving the illumination conditions for objects like satellites during these hours. As the Earth rotates and night progresses, the Western horizon moves out of sight and fewer satellites become visible in this direction as the night becomes darker. On the other hand, since the Sun will rise in the East, the visibility of the Eastern horizon will increase towards the end of the night. Hence, as sunrise approaches, the illumination conditions become more favourable for seeing satellites in the East.

Across all cameras, we see that observations are most affected during the first and last 15–30 minutes of the observing night. This corresponds to just around the end and start of astronomical twilight, respectively, time periods where observations are impacted most by the poorer observing conditions. While science objectives are generally not targeted during twilight hours, we see that the camera FoV can still be affected post and prior to these times, meaning that observations taken during ‘peak’ observing hours are being impacted. In fact, approximately 39% of all images captured during the first and last hour of the observing night contained at least one Starlink trail. The Western part of the sky was most affected while the Northern region was least, with approximately 58% of LSW images and 16% of LSN images being contaminated, respectively. However, it is noted that the percentages of the FoV affected among all cameras are relatively low,

Figure 4.5: Bar charts showing the percentage of the FoV (per camera) affected by the presence of Starlink trails as a function of time during the night of observations. An almost 6 hour gap when no satellite detections were made is omitted by breaking the x -axes into two. In each plot, a single bar corresponds to an observation (i.e., a delta image). The labels LSN, LSS, LSW, LSE, and LSC denote the 5 different cameras which point in the North, South, West, East, and Zenith direction, respectively.

with a highest value of just 0.44%. This is even less for the total FoV (combined across all 5 cameras), with a maximum value reaching 0.18%.

Be that as it may, only 3173 Starlink satellites had been launched at the time of observation, and with measurements having been collected for 175 of them. By assuming the same relative density of Starlinks present in each observation, a rough approximation of the projected interference can be made for future population sizes. For this, the observing night is used as a reference for a ‘future’ night of observations such that the same time-range and detection frequency is adopted. The full Starlink population is projected to surpass 40 000 satellites while that of all mega-constellations combined is set to exceed 500 000 satellites¹

Using these population numbers, Figure 4.6 shows the percentage of the combined FoV estimated to be affected by mega-constellation satellites with projected population numbers. The orange bars approximate the expected Starlink population number, while the blue bars approximate the expected total population number across all mega-constellations. For the future Starlink population size, the percentages remain relatively low, with the

¹ See <https://planet4589.org/space/con/conlist.html> for updated statistics (McDowell, 2023).

Figure 4.6: Bar charts showing the projected percentage of the combined MASCARA FoV affected by satellite trails as a function of time for a representative night of observations. Mega-constellations with a population size approximating that of the expected total number of Starlinks is given in orange (40 000 satellites), while that with a population size approximating the expected combined total of all mega-constellations is shown in blue (500 000 satellites).

highest reaching a value of around 5.2%. However, the percentage of the MASCARA FoV affected can be significantly large for the projected combined total population size across all mega-constellations, with the highest value exceeding 65%. As these projections are based on the density of Starlinks detected over the particular night of observations as well as the detection quality, these approximations are crude and should be considered as order-of-magnitude estimates. That being said, the approximations are conservative and should, at the very least, serve as an example of the future level at which mega-constellations may interfere with observations if further measures to mitigate their brightness are not taken. The implication of these estimates on telescopes other than MASCARA is discussed in Section 5.2.2.

5 Discussion

5.1 Sources of uncertainty

When considering the calculation of the brightness magnitude, there are a number of factors one might expect could contribute to the total estimated uncertainty. We can distinguish these components into two broad categories; random errors and systematic errors. As discussed in Section 3.3.1, photon noise and readout noise add to the contribution of random errors. Other factors may include random variations of the background sky due to atmospheric conditions or random artefacts from the processes involved for creating delta images and extracting trails, where misalignment errors or inconsistent levels of precision may lead to random residuals that contribute towards the uncertainty on the magnitude. Systematic noise refers to any noise source that introduces consistent and reproducible errors or biases in the observations. Important sources to consider include calibration errors and instrumental effects due to the imperfections associated with the camera’s construction. As a result, the varying sensitivity of the camera sensor can introduce biases and systematic offsets that may interfere with the magnitude calculation. These sources may contribute to the uncertainty on the few-percent level, and so are corrected for during the standard data reduction process by taking calibration frames and applying them to the data (Talens et al., 2018). Examples of these include bias frames and flat fields.

Bias frames are images taken with the camera’s shutter closed over a zero exposure time. With no signal received from external sources, this allows for intrinsic electronic offsets or biases of the detector to be recorded. The average of these bias frames is then subtracted from the data to help remove the contribution of these noise sources and enhance the true signal. Any error arising from dark current noise is compensated for in a similar way. Dark current frames are recorded through images taken with a closed shutter over the typical exposure time of 6.4 seconds, where the average of these frames is then subtracted from the data. Since the extent of dark current is proportional to the exposure time, its contribution is low due to the relatively short exposure time of the camera.

Flat fields are images taken with a uniformly distributed light source illuminating the camera’s detector. By creating a constant level of illumination across the FoV, this reveals

the sensitivity variations of the imaging system. The detector’s pixel-to-pixel response can be normalized by dividing the data by flat fields, helping to correct non-uniformities in the system and reduce their contribution to the uncertainty measurement.

It is noted that other sources of uncertainty possibly exist and a more in-depth treatment should be carried out to better evaluate and compensate for their contribution. This could include a more thorough analysis of systematic offsets introduced by things like hot pixels or from the subtraction procedures used when creating delta images. In particular, a potentially significant contribution to the uncertainty may be derived from the different methods of aperture photometry used in this work. Aperture photometry is often employed when measuring the brightness of astronomical objects, and it involves selecting a specific aperture to measure the total flux of the object. Errors on the order of several percent can be introduced when the choice of aperture used is not consistent across each measurement.

In our case, a circular aperture was adopted for determining the flux of the reference stars while a more elliptical and elongated one was used for measuring the flux of the satellite trails. The size and shape of each annulus can affect the amount of light being measured that is enclosed within the aperture. Hence, when estimating the brightness magnitude of the satellite trail, it is not fair to directly compare the measured flux of the stars to that of the trail since the flux may be over- or under- estimated depending on the choice of aperture used. A way to account for this could involve looking at measurements of the trail brightness for a single satellite. As the elliptical annuli adopted for the trails are larger and more spread out, the measured flux is likely underestimated when compared to the more point-like nature of the aperture used for the reference stars. Furthermore, the elliptical aperture may not perfectly match the shape and orientation of the trail, leading to variations in the measured flux. Finding time-sequences of a satellite (i.e., when the same satellite moves across the FoV over many exposures) that exhibit a near-constant brightness measurement could help to place an upper limit on the error introduced. This could be used to apply an aperture correction to help adjust the measured fluxes to a common aperture, thereby reducing the effects introduced by the aperture difference.

5.2 Future work

5.2.1 Improvements and additional considerations

While this study has provided valuable insights, there are still areas that remain unexplored or warrant further investigation. Firstly, many of our procedures could be refined to improve their performance. The routine developed for assessing the visibility of a satellite is not perfect and a number of false detections were noted, where a false detection refers to a non-visible satellite that was predicted to be visible in the camera’s

FoV. Although this does not have a significant impact on the quality of this work, it begs the question of why false detections are being made. Further conditions to assess the illumination of a satellite could be implemented to better predict its visibility, such as considering the atmospheric conditions. An argument could be made that there is in-fact an illuminated satellite present in a ‘false’ detection, but it is simply not being detected due to the limited detection limit as determined by the signal-to-noise ratio between the satellite trail and background. In that case, these satellites could be considered unimportant as they would not be bright enough to affect observations in a meaningful way. However, this is particular to MASCARA and it is worth exploring further if one were to use these routines with data collected from different telescopes. The reasons stated here are likely why Starlink trails were not extracted for 1737 of the images within our reduced subset, as noted in Section 4.

The routines for trail detection and extraction could also be improved upon. The implementation of the Hough Transform and RANSAC methods are not perfect and often struggle to deduce whether or not detected line segments should belong to the same satellite trail. Furthermore, gaps in the trail due to random noise and stars that have been masked away can lead to detections of lines that are incomplete. As discussed in Section 3.3.2, a workaround to this problem was found that merged and connected lines together based on the positions of the satellite as determined from its TLE. However, for this to be fully effective, it requires detections of lines that include the end-points of the trail. This meant that trails were not fully realised for detections where this was not the case.

An improvement to this procedure could be made by considering the line detection threshold parameters in more detail. These are used to define the limits for when and how detected lines should be combined or extended to better complete them. As satellites in LEO exhibit similar trail characteristics, constant threshold values were chosen. However, this one-size-fits-all approach begins to break down if gaps in the lines exist and the approximation no longer remains reasonable. A solution to this issue could include a routine that adaptively adjusts these parameters based on the particular observation. This would require prior information about the satellite’s location and trail length, which could be provided by its TLE. Alternatively, other methods for trail detection could be explored, such as those involving machine learning or deep learning techniques. Having risen in popularity in recent years, these approaches have been shown to excel at feature extraction in images (Elharrouss et al., 2022).

When computing the brightness magnitude for a trail, a condition was set to disregard the observation if the measured trail length was not sufficiently complete (i.e., when compared to the TLE length). This was done to increase the reliability of the final set of measurements since the flux measured for an incomplete trail may not be an appropriate representation of its brightness. When investigating the relationship between the measured flux and length of a trail in Section 3.5, the potential for deriving a scaling

factor for the flux was noted. This would be done to bring the measured flux for an incomplete trail to a value that was more representative of the trail if its full length had been extracted. In doing so, there is the possibility of retaining observations that were previously disregarded due to having an insufficient measured trail length, thereby increasing the amount of usable data for analysis. Hence, a scaling factor for the trail flux based on its length is something worth exploring in future work.

5.2.2 Beyond MASCARA

The assessment of interference to science objectives was done in the context of MASCARA only. While this serves as a representative case, it would be insightful to extend this analysis to other ground-based optical telescopes and specifically to those conducting wide-field sky surveys as these are expected to be most impacted by trails from mega-constellations (Mróz *et al.*, 2022). This could be of particular interest to the Vera C. Rubin Observatory and its planned Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST; Ivezić *et al.* 2019). Scheduled to begin in 2024, LSST will take 30s exposures of the deep sky every night for 10 years, with the ability to discern objects down to a limiting magnitude of 24.5. The Rubin Observatory will also have the highest light-gathering power of any existing or planned optical facility (Tyson *et al.*, 2020b). This refers to the telescope’s ability to collect light from a wide area, something that is crucial in capturing more photons from distant or faint sources.

However, this means that Rubin/LSST observations may be heavily susceptible to interference from mega-constellations. Hainaut & Williams (2020) found that 30% of exposures collected during twilight would be affected from satellite trails belonging to a simulated mega-constellation of 80 000 satellites, while Tyson *et al.* (2020b) simulated a population of 48 000 satellites and found that about 1% of pixels in LSST nautical twilight images would be affected. Both of these studies used the Starlink network as a reference for the mega-constellations simulated. Using the more recent Starlink observations presented in this study, future work could be done to investigate the potential interference to Rubin/LSST observations caused by mega-constellations. Additionally, this could be done with the more recent estimation for the total future population size across all mega-constellations, which is projected to exceed 500 000 satellites. In doing so would provide further insight into the level at which ground-based optical telescopes and wide-field sky surveys may be impacted by mega-constellations.

5.2.3 Additional data

While the results presented here is limited to data collected from a single observing night, the routines developed are not and can be easily applied to further observations. Therefore, future work that broadens this study by including data from multiple nights

should be done to gain a deeper understanding of the typical level of interference caused. As the visibility of satellites and hence their likelihood of being detected in observations is dependent on the time of year, expanding the data range over several months would allow for a more in-depth investigation as a function of time. The larger dataset would also allow for an improved statistical analysis of the satellite trails, helping to better understand any correlations between their visibility and orbital parameters. In particular, a larger dataset would enable for a detailed investigation of the satellite brightness as a function of its phase angle (i.e., the angle between the observer and the Sun as seen from the satellite). As a satellite moves along its orbit, the amount of light reflected towards the observer will vary due to the change in its phase angle. Studies have shown the phase angle to be an important property for assessing the brightness of a satellite and how it varies over time (e.g., [Mallama & Respler 2022](#); [Johnson et al. 2021](#)).

Furthermore, future work should include more recent data to acquire a more up-to-date characterization of the interference. Since the night of observations in October 2022, the number of launched Starlinks has increased by over 50%, bringing the total to 4881 (as of July 2023¹). Additional v1.5 Starlinks have been since deployed, as well as the first few batches of the next generation. These v2 Starlinks have design modifications which include a second-generation dielectric mirror film which SpaceX claims to be 10x better at reducing the observed brightness compared to the previous design on-board the v1.5 satellites ([SpaceX, 2022](#)). Applying the work done in this study to more recent observations could therefore provide new insights into the effectiveness of the brightness mitigations further introduced to Starlink.

Finally, mega-constellations other than Starlink should be considered in the future. The Airbus OneWeb mega-constellation has increased their deployment strategy since October 2022, with over 600 satellites now launched into orbit¹. The inclusion of these satellites in future work should provide an improved understanding of the interference that may be caused by the variety of satellites in different mega-constellations.

¹ See <https://planet4589.org/space/con/conlist.html> for updated statistics ([McDowell, 2023](#)).

6 Conclusions

In this thesis project, the interference from mega-constellation satellites on ground-based astronomy was investigated using the MASCARA instrument. Equipped with an exposure and cadence time of 6.4 seconds, this wide-field imaging array enabled a detailed study of the trails left behind in observations from these satellites, offering key insights into their impact on scientific operations. Due to its large population size which closely approximated the total number of satellites deployed across all mega-constellations at the time, this study focused on the interference caused by the Starlink satellite network.

Firstly, automated procedures for the tracking and detection of satellites in observational data were both developed and extended. This included a routine for assessing the visibility of a satellite by estimating the level at which it is illuminated relative to a ground observer at a particular time. A range of orbital parameters were explored when establishing the illumination conditions for this method, and properties such as the satellite's position, altitude, and elevation of the Sun were found to be important factors. Satellite trails were then made recognisable in the data through the process of superimposing and subtracting two successive observations. Following this, routines for detecting trails and extracting them from the background noise were adapted to the specific demands of this work and improvements to their operation were made. This included procedures for line detection, noise suppression, and for increasing the contrast between trail and background. Methods for computing the visual brightness magnitude of the trails by comparing their measured flux to that of reference stars were implemented and the result, along with various attributes related to the observation, were recorded for analysis.

Using data collected over a single night of observations, trails belonging to Starlink satellites were successfully extracted from 1282 images, with a total of 1605 separate trail measurements for 175 unique Starlink satellites. After normalizing the brightness magnitudes to a common range of 1000 km, the average magnitude over all observations was found to be 5.8 ± 0.10 with a standard deviation of 0.95. The VisorSat and Darksat Starlink designs were also investigated, finding average magnitudes of 5.6 ± 0.10 and 6.6 ± 0.09 , respectively. These magnitudes are all brighter than the goal set by the SATCON1 workshop, which advocates for satellites to be fainter than $m_v = 7$. When further investigating the types of Starlink, an average magnitude of 5.9 ± 0.09 was found

for the v1.5 design, the latest version deployed at the time of observation. While its design was reported to mitigate its brightness better than its predecessors, we see that its magnitude exceeds that of DarkSat and failed to meet the recommendation by SAT-CON1, with approximately 99% of the 667 v1.5 observations brighter than the $m_v = 7$ limit. We therefore conclude that the mitigation strategies adopted by SpaceX have not been sufficient enough in reducing the reflectivity of their satellites. However, it is noted that second-generation Starlinks have since been launched with further modifications to decrease their brightness. The effectiveness of this new design remains to be seen.

Observations taken in the first and last hour of the night were found to be most affected by Starlink trails. This corresponded to when the Sun was at an elevation between 18 and 34 degrees below the horizon (i.e., $-34^\circ < A_\odot < -18^\circ$), thereby coinciding with our understanding of the illumination conditions for a satellite and how its visibility will decline as it enters the Earth’s shadow. During this window, approximately 39% of images taken across all cameras contained at least one Starlink trail. As these observations fall outside of twilight hours, it can be concluded that the presence of these trails have the potential to hinder science objectives. To better quantify the extent of this interference, the percentage of the FoV obscured by trails was investigated. This was found to be relatively low, with the highest value between each camera reaching 0.44%. For the combined FoV across all cameras, a maximum value of just 0.18% was obtained.

However, the level of contamination significantly increases when future population sizes are considered. Using the density and frequency of Starlinks detected over the night of observations as a reference, the percentage of the total MASCARA FoV obscured by trails was determined for projected population numbers. For the full Starlink population of 40 000 satellites, this value reached a maximum of 5.2%, whereas a maximum exceeding 65% was found for the combined future population size across all mega-constellations (500 000 satellites). For the latter projection, this means that hundreds of satellites could be visible in MASCARA observations at peak observing times, which may lead to the entire area outside of the Earth’s shadow becoming unusable. While these results should be considered as order-of-magnitude approximations, they are conservative and under-represent the expected future population sizes. Hence, this assessment is likely to be optimistic, and the level of interference could very well exceed these estimates.

The goal of this research was to assess the level of interference, if any, from mega-constellation satellites on ground-based optical astronomy. The extent of this was characterized using observations collected from the MASCARA wide-field instrument and using the Starlink mega-constellation as a test case. From the results presented here, it is clear that these LEO satellites have the ability to frequently contaminate MASCARA images. The measured brightness magnitudes of the detected Starlink trails are substantial enough to obscure observations and potentially hinder science objectives. While the design strategies adopted by SpaceX have helped in reducing the brightness, additional

considerations are needed to minimize the impact on future observations. Without further mitigations, mega-constellations with population sizes expected in the near-future could significantly interfere with ground-based observations.

These results provide insight into the scale of interference caused by mega-constellations and offer valuable information for large ground-based surveys to consider. Timely mitigation strategies should be developed before science operations are disrupted, and to ensure the preservation of uninterrupted astronomical research.

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Appendices

A Tabulated Starlink properties

Table A1: Example of the attributes recorded for each Starlink observation. Shown here is the name of the satellite, the Julian Date (JD) fraction specifying the time of observation, the measured visual brightness magnitude m_v of the trail, the orbital height H , the range r between MASCARA and the satellite, the orbital inclination i , the altitude A and azimuth az of the satellite, and the altitude A_\odot and azimuth az_\odot of the Sun. Additional properties related to the satellite and its orbit that are not shown here were also recorded. This table is available in its entirety in machine-readable form via <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8199567>.

Name	JD	m_v (mag)	H (km)	r (km)	i (deg)	A (deg)	az (deg)	A_\odot (deg)	az_\odot (deg)	...
STARLINK-2598	2459876.528275058	6.05 ± 0.08	556.32	579.34	53.05	72.23	263.99	-21.79	241.72	...
STARLINK-1541	2459876.831075677	4.79 ± 0.22	555.84	1168.13	53.06	23.76	73.17	-24.92	121.22	...
STARLINK-3753	2459876.828859612	5.14 ± 0.23	552.75	1153.68	53.22	24.02	152.49	-25.52	121.78	...
STARLINK-1466	2459876.535883883	6.43 ± 0.19	559.63	1063.97	53.06	27.58	172.38	-23.87	239.89	...
STARLINK-3068	2459876.545191614	6.61 ± 0.11	582.11	873.48	70.00	38.70	188.27	-26.37	237.54	...
STARLINK-3048	2459876.549845596	6.14 ± 0.12	582.76	869.10	70.00	39.05	206.67	-27.59	236.31	...
STARLINK-1559	2459876.843264595	4.13 ± 0.19	560.40	1131.48	53.05	25.20	187.63	-21.60	118.26	...
STARLINK-2526	2459876.551175398	5.31 ± 0.06	557.14	931.38	53.05	33.27	238.23	-27.94	235.96	...
STARLINK-3930	2459876.834917019	4.78 ± 0.22	548.47	1187.34	53.22	22.74	62.66	-23.88	120.27	...
STARLINK-3055	2459876.564102841	5.25 ± 0.11	582.67	1147.25	70.00	26.03	233.43	-31.23	232.33	...
...

Figure B1: A delta image containing the Starlink trail with the brightest measured magnitude, as indicated by the red circle. When scaled to a range of 1000 km, the magnitude was computed as $m_v = 2.9 \pm 0.04$.

B Bright outliers

As noted in Section 4.1, an outlier with a significantly bright measured magnitude was found. The delta image for which this detection was obtained is shown in Figure B1, as highlighted by the red circle. The notable brightness of the satellite is obvious in the image, with a significant contrast between the trail and background. Interestingly, this trail was found to belong to STARLINK-2735, a VisorSat that was launched in May 2021. In total, four observations were made of this satellite over the particular camera. When scaled to a range of 1000 km, these were calculated as a function of time to be 2.9 ± 0.04 , 3.0 ± 0.03 , 3.5 ± 0.05 , and 3.5 ± 0.04 , with a standard deviation of 0.27 magnitudes. To better inspect this variation in magnitude, the detected trail length was compared to the length as determined from the TLE, where a similar variation was found. The first two measurements very closely approximated the TLE length, while the second two extracted a similar length that was around 25% shorter. Hence, the trend in the measured magnitude can likely be attributed to the length of the trail as detected by the CCD, thereby strengthening the validity of these measurements.